

Galvanostatic and Chronopotentiometric Study of the Oxidation of Ethyl Alcohol at Platinized Platinum Electrode*

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The oxidation of ethyl alcohol was studied at platinized platinum electrode in acid medium using Galvanostatic method at steady-state condition and chronopotentiometric method. The data indicate that the process is activation controlled. The system was studied at different temperatures and the energy of activation was found to be 14 K. cal mole⁻¹. The rate was found to depend on concentration of ethanol up to the concentration of 1.5M and above this, the rate was independent of concentration. The observed Tafel slope of 120 mv per decade was not dependent either on concentration of ethanol or temperature up to the potential 0.8V. Potential oscillations were observed at higher potentials. The exchange current density was found to be about 10⁻⁶ A cm⁻² at 28°. pH was found to have no effect on the rate.

Chronopotentiometric results were interpreted as that two electrons were involved in the oxidation process and the oxidation of the adsorbed species was the rate determining step. The effect of molybdate ion and the product acetaldehyde on the rate was studied. A probable mechanism was put forward for the electrochemical oxidation of ethanol.

THE work reported here is a part of the study of the basic mechanism of oxidation of liquid organic compounds which can be used in fuel cells. In the present paper the oxidation of a typical fuel, ethanol on platinized platinum in sulphuric acid was studied.

Several studies have been reported on the oxidation of ethanol at platinum during recent years¹⁻⁵. Rightmore et al.¹ proposed a fast chemisorption step involving charge transfer followed by a rate determining electrochemical step.

Gileadi and Pierzma² derived kinetic equations assuming that the first step is in pre-equilibrium but were unable to explain all the reported experimental results. They assumed that, poisoning of the surface at higher potential was due to the formation of oxide layer on the surface of the electrode. Liang et al.³ deduced the initial chemisorption step was rate determining step. Blake et al.⁴ in their mechanistic studies discussed all the possible mechanisms suggested by Rightmore, Frumkin, Brumer and finally Bockris⁵ widely accepted generalized mechanism for a variety of anodic oxidations, especially hydrocarbons, in the light of their findings. Podlovchenko et al.⁵ postulated that if ethanol is introduced at an electrode registering a

potential in the double layer, the scission of the bond occurs. They proposed a possible mechanism which involved a number of free radicals in the reaction scheme.

In the present paper Galvanostatic and Chronopotentiometric methods were used for the determination of mechanism; the latter method, was used for the determination of the type of the reaction, number of electrons involved in the oxidation process and fractional coverage of the adsorbed species at open circuit potential. The effect of molybdate ion (Mo⁶⁺) as a catalyst (redox catalyst) on the rate was studied using Galvanostatic and Chronopotentiometric methods. The effect of the oxidation product of ethanol namely, acetaldehyde was studied on the rate.

Experimental

The electrochemical cell used was described previously⁶. The details of the Galvanostatic technique were given elsewhere⁷. The test electrode and the auxiliary electrode consisted of platinum foil of 2 cm² geometric area. The process of cleaning the electrode, and the procedure for the deposition of platinum was mentioned earlier⁸. The electrode was activated just prior to use by electrochemical pulsing technique⁹. The sulphuric acid was of 'AnalaR' quality and it was diluted using triply distilled conductivity water. Ethanol was refluxed and distilled thrice and the middle portion was taken. The sulphuric acid solution was pre-electrolysed at a current density of 20 mA cm⁻² for

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24 hours in nitrogen atmosphere using platinized platinum foil electrode to remove the impurities (especially organic impurities). Any trace of oxygen present in the test solution was removed by passing purified nitrogen gas. After stopping the flow of nitrogen gas the system was kept undisturbed to attain equilibrium. Then the current-potential readings were noted at steady-state.

In chronopotentiometric single pulse method, the test electrode used was of platinized platinum wire, whose geometric surface area was 0.1 cm^2 , and the counter electrode of 2 cm^2 platinized platinum foil. The details of the set up were given already⁷. In this system a constant current was passed through the test electrode and the auxiliary electrode for a small period using mercury contact switch. The input attenuator of y amplifier of the oscilloscope was set at 0.2 V div^{-1} and the time base was varied from 1 sec. div^{-1} to $3 \text{ milli sec. div}^{-1}$. The current density used was varied from 1 mA cm^{-2} to 500 mA cm^{-2} . The oscilloscopic traces were photographed using a camera, from which the transition times were measured¹⁰.

The system was studied at different concentrations of the fuel and the observed values were compared with the hydrogen charging curve. The effect of molybdate ion was studied on the oxidation of ethanol using Galvanostatic as well as Chronopotentiometric methods. For the determination of open circuit potential a freshly anodized electrode was kept in the test solution and the variation of potential with time was noted till a steady value was obtained¹¹.

All the current density readings were reported on the basis of geometric area and all potentials were referred to the normal hydrogen electrode. Temperature effects were studied using thermostat with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Unless otherwise specified all the readings were taken using 1 M sulphuric acid and at temperature 28° .

Results and Discussion

(a) *Kinetic Parameters* : Tafel plots were drawn for the system at different concentrations of the fuel. Fig. 1 was the plot of log. of the concentration of ethanol against log. current density, from which we can conclude that above 1.5 M of ethanol the order of reaction with respect to ethanol was zero, whereas below 1.5 M the order is one. Increase of temperature was found to decrease the polarization as is shown in the fig. 2. The energy of activation is found from the slope of the plot of log. current density against inverse temperature¹², to be $14 \text{ K.cal. mole}^{-1}$ at open circuit potential. $p\text{H}$ was found to have no effect on the rate. The Tafel slope for the platinized platinum electrode was found to be approximately 120 mV per decade at lower potentials, similar to the observations of Blake et al⁴. This slope was found to be almost constant irrespective of the changes of $p\text{H}$, concentration of ethyl alcohol and temperature. At potentials

above 0.7 V , the slope was found to change rapidly to higher values. The Tafel plot for the oxidation of ethanol at platinized platinum electrode at different concentrations of ethanol and at different temperatures is shown in the Fig. 3. At higher potentials (about 0.8 Volt Vs NHE) formation of the oxide layer over platinum takes place limiting the Tafel region. The oxidation of ethanol through oxides of platinum may be a slow process. Potential oscillations were observed at still higher potentials. The exchange current density was found to be about $10^{-6} \text{ A. cm}^{-2}$ which was obtained by extending the curve in the Tafel plot to the reversible potential calculated from thermodynamic data¹³. The effect of molybdate ion as a redox catalyst, and the effect of the oxidation product of ethanol namely acetaldehyde, on the rate of electrochemical oxidation of ethanol is shown in the Fig. 4.

Fig 1 : Logarithm of concentration of ethyl alcohol against logarithm of current density at constant over potential (at 0.50 V) at platinized platinum electrode using 1 M sulphuric acid at 28°C .

Fig. 2 : Current-potential diagram of 1 M ethyl alcohol and 1 M sulphuric acid at platinized platinum electrode at different temperatures.

Fig. 3: Logarithm of current density vs over voltage at platinumized platinum electrode in 1M sulphuric acid at different concentrations of ethyl alcohol and at different temperatures.

Fig. 4: Current-potential diagram at platinumized platinum electrode in 1M sulphuric acid and 1M ethyl alcohol, and with the addition of (i) acetaldehyde and (ii) molybdate Mo⁺₆ at 28°C.

(b) *Chronopotentiometric Observations*: Chronopotentiometric charging curves were taken in pre-electrolysed sulphuric acid solution, saturated with hydrogen gas. The quantity of charge $i\tau$ required to ionize the monolayer of adsorbed hydrogen was found to be 40 mc cm⁻², which was constant for the electrode at different currents. The value of roughness factor about 200, compared to the ordinary value¹⁴ of approximately 1000 may be due to the small amount of platinum deposited. The roughness factor was calculated on the basis of 0.21 mc/cm², the charge required for the ionization of monolayer of adsorbed hydrogen¹⁴. The product $i\tau$ ^{11,12} was found to increase continuously with increase of current density, as is given in the Table which indicates that the process is not diffusion controlled¹⁵. The charging curves in ethanol were

taken by keeping the electrode in ethanol-sulphuric acid solution starting from open circuit potential. The quantity of charge required to ionize the adsorbed organic was found to be about 77 mc cm⁻². Similar to that of hydrogen charging curves, the product $i\tau$ ^{11,12} is not constant, as is given in the table and was increasing continuously as the current was increased. This indicates that the process of oxidation of ethanol is not diffusion controlled and also not controlled by chemical reaction and the process is not accompanied by electro capillary convection. The slope of the graph from the plot of $i\tau$ ^{11,12} vs i is positive, which shows that the process is controlled by the oxidation of the adsorbed species¹⁶ which is produced by extremely fast rates of adsorption and desorption of the organic species so that equilibrium is maintained between solution species of the electrode, and the species on the surface¹⁷. The oxidation of the adsorbed species is not mixed with diffusion according to Laitinen et al¹⁸. The value of $i\tau$ is constant with in $\pm 7\%$ error in approximation of measuring the transition time.

The transition times observed in the charging curves were started at open circuit potential and limited at approximately 0.75V, above which the formation of oxide layer begins. The potential limit indicates that the oxidation process is ceased above this value when the reaction is inhibited by the oxide layer formed on the electrode surface. This result is in support of Gilardi and Piersma's assumption². The charging curves which were photographed indicate that the double layer charging which is negligible¹⁹ is also included in the oxidation process, as is shown in the Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Potential-time diagram (chronopotentiometric single pulse) at platinumized platinum in 1M sulphuric acid and 1M ethyl alcohol at 28°C.

It was observed that the charge required to oxidize the adsorbed ethanol on an electrode is almost double to that required for ionization of the adsorbed hydrogen on the same electrode. So it is likely that two electrons are involved in the electro-oxidation of ethanol in the Tafel region. It was observed that the presence of

TABLE SHOWING THE CHRONOPOTENTIOMETRIC DATA

Sl. No.	Chronopotentiometric results of hydrogen gas saturated 1M sulphuric acid solution				Chronopotentiometric results of test solution containing 1M ethanol and 1M sulphuric acid			
	i in mA	τ in sec.	$i\tau$	$i\tau^{1/2}$	i in mA	τ in sec.	$i\tau$	$i\tau^{1/2}$
1.	2.0	20	40	8.94	18	4	72	36
2.	5.5	8	44	15.57	36	2.1	75.6	52.2
3.	12.0	3.3	39.6	21.84	54	1.5	81.0	65.88
4.	20.0	2.0	40.0	28.2	72	1.0	72.0	72.0
5.	30.0	1.2	36.0	33.0	90	0.9	81.0	85.5
6.	40.0	1.0	40.0	40.0	110	0.7	77.0	92.4
7.	50.0	0.8	40.0	45.0	130	0.6	78.0	100.1
8.	100.0	0.4	40.0	63.0	150	0.5	75.0	106.5
9.	150.0	0.27	40.5	78	250	0.3	75.0	137.5
10.	200.0	0.2	40.0	90.0	350	0.24	84.0	171.5

additional acetaldehyde in various concentrations did not change the polarization characteristics of ethanol oxidation. So acetaldehyde was neither adsorbed nor oxidized on the platinized platinum electrode in the observed potential range. The fractional surface area covered by the adsorbed species will be approximately 0.8 and this value is similar to that given by Blake et al⁴.

(c) *Open Circuit Potentials* : The standard reversible potential calculated from thermodynamic data for ethanol oxidation is $E^0 = 0.17V$. Rest potential of the order of 0.20V was observed in 1M sulphuric acid solution. These values were found to vary from 0.15V to 0.25V, which may be due to the pre-treatment of the electrode.

From the chronopotentiometric single pulse method it was found that the potential of the electrode in ethanol falls to a minimum after anodic pulse was given and then rises to open circuit potential. This minimum potential corresponds almost to 0.0V, which immediately increases to the open circuit potential of about 0.15V within 1 to 2 seconds. This observed potential minimum, similar to that of formic acid, formaldehyde etc^{11,20}, was found to be highly dependent on the pre-treatment of the electrode. The minimum in the open circuit potential can be attributed to a mixed potential between hydrogen, resulting from dissociation of ethanol and some organic species²¹. These observations lead to the following scheme for the open circuit decay in ethanol of the platinum electrode being anodized to 1.0V initially

similar type of reactions for formic acid¹¹, at platinum electrode were suggested.

(d) *Mechanism of the Reaction* : The observed Tafel slope of about 120 mv per decade indicates that the first electron transfer is the rate determining step. If we write the oxidation of ethanol as

considering step 2 as the rate determining step and applying Langmuir type of adsorption, the rate equation can be expressed as

$$v = k\theta_T \exp\left(\frac{\beta VF}{RT}\right)$$

where θ_T is the coverage of the adsorbed species, the other terms having their usual significance. Considering step 1 is in equilibrium as supported by chronopotentiometric results, the above rate expression can be rewritten as, after substituting the value of θ_T from the step 1,

$$v = k' C_{C_2H_5OH} (1 - \theta_T) \exp\left(\frac{\beta VF}{RT}\right)$$

The rate equation satisfies the observed Tafel slope, first order reaction with respect to ethanol and the independence of rate with pH of the solution.

The rate equation indicates that the order of the reaction with respect to ethanol is one. But according to the observed values it was found that at higher concentrations of ethanol the order was tending to zero. The first order reaction with respect to ethanol was found up to the concentration of approximately 0.3M by Liang et al.³, and 0.5M by Sunderland et al.⁴, on bright platinum and in the present investigation about 1.5M on the platinized platinum. This increase in the limiting concentration of ethanol compared to the previous values may be due to the increase of surface area of platinized platinum compared to the bright platinum.

Assuming the fraction of the electrode surface covered by the species other than ethanol, like $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}_{\text{ad}}$, $\text{CH}_2\text{OH}_{\text{ad}}$, CHOH_{ad} , etc.⁵ remaining constant and low and considering θ_T , which is almost equal to $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}-\text{Pt}$, reaching to limiting value as the concentration of the ethanol increased to 1.5M, the rate expression becomes independent of the concentration of ethanol.

It was known that at potentials higher than 0.8V, the formation of oxide layer begins on the electrode^{2,2}, which can be expressed as

At these potentials the oxide layer formation begins also from the adsorbed ethanol species as suggested¹,

so, as the potential is increased from open circuit to about 0.70V the reaction steps 1, 2 and 3 will occur. But as the potential is increased to still higher values, oxide layer formation occurs through steps 4 to 7 decreasing the available sites for ethanol to adsorb. This type of blocking of surface by the oxide layer decreases the value of θ_T to low value, which on the other hand decreases rate of oxidation. The occurrence of this type of multistep reactions at higher potentials may be causing a change in the Tafel slope from 120 mv to higher values.

The potential oscillations which were observed at still higher potential might be considered due to the formation of oxide layer on the electrode by electrochemical process as indicated and simultaneous chemical

reduction of the so formed oxide layer by ethyl alcohol. At higher potentials electrochemical process predominates the chemical process, thereby making the oxide layer formation irreversible. This makes the electrode inactive for the oxidation to occur.

(e) *The Effect of Molybdate Ion on the Rate:* In the presence of molybdate ion in ethanol-sulphuric acid solution the product $i_T^{1/2}$ was found to be constant and independent of current. The $i_T^{1/2}$ was found to be dependent on the concentration of molybdate ion and was increasing proportionally with increasing concentration of molybdate ion. This indicates that the process was controlled by the diffusion of that ion^{1,6}. The polarization in the oxidation of ethanol in presence of molybdate ion was found to be considerably high as is shown in the Fig. 4. So it appears that the chemical reaction^{2,8}

is the slow step in the electrochemical oxidation of the ethanol at platinized platinum electrode in presence of molybdate ion. Mo^{+5} being subsequently oxidized to Mo^{+6} at the electrode.

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